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Governing the European Green Deal Through Local Social Experiments

Part of the Collection: Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes

October 2025

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Executive summary of recommendations

The SHARED GREEN DEAL project involved undertaking 24 social experiments across Europe to stimulate actions on the European Green Deal. Through ‘learning by doing,’ social experiment participants tested social sciences and humanities tools to address key Green Deal topics: Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food, and Preserving Biodiversity.

This report analyses how the social experiments contribute to our understanding of the governance of the European Green Deal at the local level. It draws on the framework of experimental climate governance, which proposes that actors in local contexts continually undertake a diverse set of ongoing processes, mechanisms, and measures to probe the ways in which climate change can be prevented, mitigated, or adapted to (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014).

In the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments, local actors made the European Green Deal actionable in their contexts. They largely framed this policy in terms of local challenges: environmental and health conditions, lack of education and awareness, economic unsustainability, unsustainable practices or behaviours, lack of inclusion and participation, disconnected actors, and policy gaps. To address these, they implemented a range of educational, relational, organisational, and policy inclusion innovations. These attempts to change how people learn, form networks, organise structures, and impact policymaking contributed to longer-term shifts in public engagement in some cases.

Overall, the report finds that social experimentation can enable local actors to govern the European Green Deal. However, to do so effectively, they must embed social experiments in ongoing governance processes and funding streams, devote significant time to relationship building, and successfully navigate unexpected developments.

Based on our analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments, this report highlights the following recommendations for policymakers and governments to consider:

European Union policymakers

1. Identify and share the local and diverse ways in which the European Green Deal is already being interpreted and implemented.
2. Publicly recognise the role of local social experiments in achieving the European Green Deal and use them to inform understandings of this policy framework at the EU level.
3. Identify additional ways to incorporate support for local efforts to govern the European Green Deal into policy, research, and funding, such as ensuring that new EU Missions and Climate Contracts integrate social experimentation as a core delivery method.
4. Work with local experimenters to create a social experiment support body that can advise them on methods and activities, facilitate the sharing of best practices, and help them work through unexpected developments and challenges.

National, local, and regional policymakers, general

5. Demonstrate support for social experiments and similar initiatives by leading them, taking part in them, supporting their outcomes, or implementing policies and regulations that facilitate their work.

National, local, and regional policymakers, running social experiments

6. Embed social experiments in ongoing processes and ensure they can continue or be built upon after the 'experiment' ends.
7. Engage in the conflicts, diversity of perspectives, and relationship dynamics of social experiments rather than focusing exclusively on effective project management.
8. Co-create unique local social experiments with local and community-based actors based on proven methodologies to multiply the successes of experimental governance across contexts.
9. Create internal structures or processes for collecting, retaining, and sharing learning from experimental processes to aid governance transformation.
10. Join networks of social experimenters to exchange experiences with peers and enhance the cohesion of the collective movement towards experimental governance of the European Green Deal.

We also include recommendations for researchers and funders.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Introducing the project

This report presents findings from **Cross-topic comparisons, scaling and synthesis**, building upon previous work packages of the project ‘*Social sciences and Humanities for Achieving a Responsible, Equitable and Desirable Green Deal*’ (SHARED GREEN DEAL). The European Green Deal is a programme of policies aimed at overcoming climate change and environmental degradation by transforming the European Union (EU) into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy. The goal of SHARED GREEN DEAL is to stimulate behavioural, social and cultural change across Europe, aligned with the policy priorities of the Green Deal.

SHARED GREEN DEAL provides Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) tools to support the implementation of the Green Deal programme. In the past, SSH research on green transitions has focused on changes to either individuals (‘micro’ phenomena) or systems and collectives (‘macro’ phenomena). In contrast, SHARED GREEN DEAL focuses on ‘middle range’ (‘meso’) changes to bridge these two sets of understandings and priorities (Foulds et al., 2025). Using this innovative ‘meso’ approach, the project links societal actors to foster knowledge sharing, learn from collective experiences, and feed back into ‘macro’ policies and governance.

The SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium brings together 22 leading organisations from across Europe, including universities, research institutions, network organisations and businesses. The project is structured around **six priority Green Deal topics: Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food, and Preserving Biodiversity**. Within these six themes, a total of 24 social experiments (Figure 1.1) were delivered across different EU Member States and affiliated countries between April 2023 - June 2024, working with local municipalities and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) (Table A1.2a¹). These are called ‘local partners’ and they carried out the social experiments autonomously, with the consortium partners providing initial training and guidance, as well as support whenever needed.

The Clean Energy experiments in Denmark, Poland, Spain, and the United Kingdom undertook community visioning for clean energy futures to foster inclusive energy transitions. The Circular Economy experiments in Cyprus, France, Portugal, and Slovenia developed local accelerator hubs to spark circular business innovation through design thinking. The Efficient Renovations experiments in Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, and Spain created knowledge networks that facilitated exchange between residents and professionals, including experiential learning through home tours. The Sustainable Mobility experiments created labs in schools in Bulgaria, Ireland, Lithuania, and Portugal to identify mobility challenges and think creatively about solutions. The Sustainable Food experiments engaged stakeholders in Italy, the Netherlands, Slovakia, and Sweden in transition assemblies to identify pathways to food systems change. The Preserving Biodiversity experiments ran study circles in Greece, Ireland, Slovenia, and Sweden to explore and foster biodiversity-related values. See Appendix A1, Table A1.2a¹, for further details about each social experiment.

Other resources related to the running of and impacts from the social experiments can also be found via www.sharedgreendeal.eu.

¹ Further detail about each of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments can be found in the project’s Case Study Guides (Kovács et al., 2024).

Figure 11. Map of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments (Kóvacs et al., 2024)

1.2. Introducing the report

This report is based on a secondary analysis of data from the social experiments with the **main objective to identify how Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) priority themes cut across all six experiment streams**. The SSH priority themes are: (1) Gender and Diversity; (2) Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities; (3) Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19; (4) Governance Agendas, Framings and Conventions; (5) Geographic Differences and Evolutions across Time.

This report focuses on **governance agendas, framings and conventions** and how the social experiments have contributed to the governance of the European Green Deal at the local level. Alongside this report, four other reports were published on the respective SSH priority themes.

For the secondary analyses, a variety of data sources, collected within the social experiments, were considered (Table 1.2 below). Table A1.2.a and Table A1.2.b (in the Appendix) provide an overview of the social experiments streams and summarise the data sources in more detail, respectively.

Table 1.2. Data sources collected from social experiments considered for the secondary analysis²

Data source (#DS)	Provided by
#DS1: WP4 Codebooks of interview data with social experiments participants	SGD consortium members (WP4)
#DS2: Monthly survey (WP5 questions)	Local partners
#DS3: Monthly meeting notes (including 12th meeting)	SGD consortium members
#DS4: Final reflective surveys and experiments' journeys (Responsible Research & innovation (RRI) material)	Local partners
#DS5: RRI interviews with consortium partners	SGD consortium members
#DS6: Applications of Local Partners to host social experiments	Local partners
#DS7: Green Deal Topic Webinars	SGD consortium members

Although all data sources were reviewed, not all were equally relevant for all SSH priority themes. For this report, the data sources #DS2 (monthly surveys), #DS3 (monthly meeting notes), #DS4 (final reflective surveys and experiment journeys), and #DS6 (applications of local partners) were found particularly interesting for exploring experimental governance.

1.3. Governance agendas, framings, and conventions

In this report, we define governance as a process, following Jagers and Striiple's definition of global climate governance as: "all purposeful mechanisms and measures aimed at steering social systems towards preventing, mitigating, or adapting to the risks posed by climate change" (2003, p. 385). This definition draws attention to interventions, practices, techniques, and tactics and highlights the relational and interactional ways in which broader global or supranational governance agendas such as the European Green Deal circulate and come to be understood and implemented at smaller scales, such as the national, regional, and local levels (Barton et al., 2018; Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014).

² A more detailed version can be found in Table A1.2, in the Appendix.

Experimentation, and specifically social experimentation, which we define as “*learning by doing*” (Brown et al., 2003), is a form of climate governance, part of the “ongoing, unfolding and heterogeneous set of processes through which the will to improve is pursued” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 237). It has the potential to adapt supranational governance agendas such as the European Green Deal to the local level, through actively engaging actors in understanding what these agendas mean for their daily lives and how they can concretely address the sustainability challenges they face (Allen et al., 2023; Hoppe, 2010; Smith et al., 2017; Weisser et al., 2014).

The SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments targeting European Green Deal priority areas were participatory mechanisms to drive local change. They provide an opportunity to investigate the relationship between experiments and governance across different local and national contexts. Accounts of how local actors frame the European Green Deal and experiment with its implementation can also provide information to European and national decision-makers about the meanings of the policy in real-world contexts, valuable input that can direct the future of the European Union’s climate and sustainability policies.

Policy context: the European Green Deal

The European Green Deal, launched in 2019, is the European Union’s growth strategy, consisting of a set of policies to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. It identifies climate change and environmental degradation as key challenges and seeks to address these through “transform[ing] the EU into a fair and prosperous society, with a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy where there are no net emissions of greenhouse gases in 2050 and where economic growth is decoupled from resource use” (European Commission, 2019, p. 2). The European Green Deal aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and pollution, contributing to a healthier environment, in a fair, inclusive way. The strategy focuses on six sectoral goals to achieve this (see Appendix A2, Table A2.1) (European Commission, 2019):

1. Supplying clean, affordable and secure energy
2. Mobilising industry for a clean and circular economy
3. Building and renovating in an energy and resource efficient way
4. Accelerating the shift to sustainable and smart mobility
5. Designing a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system
6. Preserving and restoring ecosystems and biodiversity

Understanding how social experiments function as governance mechanisms in implementing these goals can better direct policy, research and funding towards projects that will make a difference in achieving the European Green Deal, addressing climate change, and improving the overall quality of life.

This report summarises the results of our analysis. In section 2, we explain the concept of experimental governance of the European Green Deal and describe our analysis process. In section 3, we present the results, focusing on how local partners understand the European Green Deal in context, what governance innovations they introduced through the social experiments, and whether and how these innovations became embedded in longer-lasting new engagement approaches. In section 4, we discuss the lessons learned and provide recommendations for policy, research, and funding. In section 5, we conclude with reflections on the implications of this analysis for the European Green Deal.

2. Conceptual and methodological approach

2.1. Conceptual lens

Although the European Green Deal is an EU-level policy, actors at the local level must implement it – and indeed, they are already doing so. This requires these actors to take general, abstract policy and make it concrete. They must frame the European Green Deal according to their local context and sustainability challenges. They must also understand who to bring together, how to bring them together, and what actions to take to successfully address the challenges.

Laws, policies, and funding provided from the international, European, national, or regional levels, as well as partnerships with other institutions and organisations, offer direction and support. Nevertheless, local level actors remain responsible for a huge portion of the experimentation, or ‘learning by doing,’ that makes up much of today’s climate governance (Brown et al., 2003; Bulkeley, 2023). To understand experimental climate governance at the local level, we draw on Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards’s (2014) concept of experimental urban climate governance:

where municipalities, private and civil society actors seek to demonstrate, experience, learn and challenge what it might mean to respond to climate change through a multiplicity of interventions, projects and schemes. Such experiments... are not simply ad hoc ventures, but need to be understood as situated and purposive interventions that demonstrate the ways in which new forms of authority are emerging in the context of climate change and the critical socio-technical dimension to realizing any governance response. (pp. 4-5)

Local actors in urban and non-urban contexts engage in a variety of experiments, which they must then maintain and incorporate into daily life to address climate and sustainability challenges (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014).

In this report, we examine three distinct stages of this process. The first is how the local partners frame the sustainability challenges they hope to address with experimental activities. Different types of “problem framings,” or “the process of defining the purpose and outcomes of innovative activity as well as delineation of the ‘thing’ that undergoes change,” allow different types of knowledge to emerge and create different “spaces for change” (Jensen et al., 2019, p. 2; Smith et al., 2010).

The second is ‘governance innovations,’ or experiment activities – proposed new methods to respond to sustainability challenges and climate change, in the social experiments. These can be described as:

a form of institutional innovation that seeks to strengthen participatory forms of governance and create new partnerships, blur the boundaries between public and private authority, and reform traditional modes of urban planning by introducing collaborative planning and integrating resilience and adaptive co-management in planning processes (Ehnert, 2023, p. 85).

Box 2.1a. Experimental governance in action: community visioning in Jaywick, UK

Essex County Council's experiment brought together community members, policymakers, and businesses whose visions for warm homes and a thriving economy in coastal Jaywick led to the launch of a community-based energy hub. The hub connects different local government offices and funding sources and offers trusted advice, helping residents to access thousands of pounds in unclaimed benefits to improve their household energy use and efficiency.

Photo: Essex County Council.

Box 2.1b. Experimental governance in action: local accelerator hub in Val-de-Marne, France

Through design thinking exercises, Val de Marne en Transition's experiment helped fashion and textile industry professionals identify the need for a community-based tailor. The organisation was able to launch the neighbourhood tailoring service Retoucherie EF94 to enhance the sustainability of garments and reduce the need for buying new ones.

Photos: Val-de-Marne en Transition

These innovations are inherently political, bringing together diverse stakeholders that may have conflicting perspectives, and raise tensions and corresponding tactics to address those tensions in place-specific ways (Manganelli, 2024a; Sengers et al., 2021).

The third is the outcome of the social experiments and how they lead to enduring engagement innovations. This is based on the idea of the ‘embedding’ of experiments: “the overall process by which outputs of experiments may come to generate wider influence beyond their initial conception and setting,” be that the ways an experiment develops after it ends, how it spreads to different geographic locations, or its cumulative effects together with other experiments (Sengers et al., 2021, p. 1155).

2.1.1. SHARED GREEN DEAL: social experimentation

Many examples of experimental climate governance start with technological innovation and address society second or as a byproduct of technological change. SHARED GREEN DEAL, on the other hand, sought to experiment with the social aspects themselves. The SHARED GREEN DEAL research consortium provided local partners with guidelines on the methods used in each experiment stream (see Table A1.2a, in the Appendix). The local partners, which had diverse backgrounds, goals and approaches, worked with the SHARED GREEN DEAL research teams to develop unique social experiments in each location. These experiments took into account the existing local governance structures and processes. The local partners in each stream received support from the research teams and each other through online and in-person interactions, including a training, a study tour to one experiment location, and an online public webinar. Although this project was initiated by and grounded in academic research, in practice it was focused on the actions taken by the local partners and other actors and contributed directly to ongoing local governance processes.

Photos: Municipality of Braga

Box 2.1c. Experimental governance in action: school mobility lab in Braga, Portugal

The municipality of Braga engaged school communities, especially students, in discussing how to get to school in more sustainable ways. They used creative arts, such as making periscopes, and wrote recommendations for safer, healthier school journeys. This led to the implementation of specific measures: a new pedestrian walkway in front of one school, fewer parking spaces in front of school buildings, and more students using public transportation.

2.2. Methodology

Our overall research question was: *What impact do experimental methods have on local, transformational governance of the European Green Deal?* Within this, we identified four specific research questions:

1. How is the European Green Deal ‘framed’ by local governments and non-governmental organisations within local contexts?
2. What European Green Deal objectives are seen as most important to local governance and why?
3. What, if any, governance innovations have been brought about by the experiments?
4. How (if at all) have the experiments shifted approaches to public engagement?

Using the digital qualitative analysis software NVivo, we first coded all themes that emerged from the data itself (focusing on data sources #DS2, #DS3, #DS4, and #DS6) (Braun and Clarke, 2023).³ We then categorised these according to the framework of “making,” “maintaining,” and “living” experiments (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014), which describes how experiments govern sustainability challenges in three overlapping stages. This allowed us to further identify which themes were most relevant to answer our research questions and examine these in greater depth. We organised our general themes into specific types of problem framings, governance innovations, and new approaches to public engagement found across the 24 social experiments (Table 2.2). A full overview of the methods used can be found in the Appendix A1.

Box 2.2. Experimental governance in action: biodiversity study circles in Tolmin, Slovenia

Posoški Razvojni Center’s experiment introduced study circles as an informal education opportunity for adults to learn about the nature around them. The group directed their own learning, choosing to study local birds and create a garden to educate the entire community on local biodiversity. After SHARED GREEN DEAL ended, they continued with a second study circle to learn more about how to run and maintain their community garden.

Photos: Posoški Razvojni Center

³ Data sources #DS1, #DS5, and #DS7 were also reviewed and informed our analysis in a less structured way.

Table 2.2. Simplified coding scheme for the governance analysis: overview of thematic categories and the respective codes applied

Code name	Description
1. MAKING experiments	This category covers codes related to the first stage of experimental urban governance: “conceiving, framing, and operationalizing the will to improve in relation to climate change” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 42). It consists of both understanding how climate change can be understood as a challenge through “problematism”, delimiting the field of intervention for acting upon the challenge, and practices to improve.
1.1 Problematism	This sub-category covers how social experiment actors understand “questions of risk and security in environmental, economic... political [and other] terms” and the “opportunities and the potential to create alternative futures” through social experiments (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 44).
1.2 Aligning multiple actors	This sub-category covers “practices of assembling a programme of improvement through which [problems] can be addressed”; “bringing into productive relation the different parties and... material elements that constitute the field of intervention” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 44).
1.3 Rendering technical	This sub-category covers the way social experiment actors “seek... to test and experience what it means to respond to climate change, and of establishing what improvement entails...” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 44). “[T]he unfolding in time and space of uncertain elements, in which the work involved in addressing climate change is contingent and bounded to a particular urban locale, yet open to multiple possibilities” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 45).
1.4 Rendering compelling	This sub-category covers the ways in which social experiment organisers “test out” how to “persuade, cajole and induce others to participate in that which is uncertain and where the rewards are unclear” and the broader “emotional and affective work” required to undertake an experiment (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 45).
2. MAINTAINING & LIVING experiments	This category refers to practices that describe how experiments, once made, are extended beyond their initial experiment period and become (or fail to become) part of everyday life.
2.1 Maintaining - upkeep and metabolic adjustment	This sub-category refers to how social experiments become practices that “are engaged in the workings of different forms of circulation and the extent that they involve ‘organizing, or anyway allowing the development of ever-wider circuits’ (Foucault 2009: 45)” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 45).
2.2 Living - conduct, subjectivity, contestation, neglect	This sub-category covers the ways in which social experiments become “taken up in the day-to-day practices of the individuals and institutions that are subject to forms of governmental intervention” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 47). Experimentation becomes a “lived practice” but also exposes its own limits. It involves the “creation of climate subjectivities, as well as the ways in which they are resisted, circumvented and ignored” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 42).

3. Main findings

This section presents the results of our analysis on governance agendas, framings, and conventions. First, we identify the ways the 24 local partners implementing the social experiments interpreted the European Green Deal to examine what this policy means at the local level and which aspects partners consider most important. Second, we show the types of activities that the organisations implemented to understand how social experiments can be governance innovations. We also look at some of the tensions these methods raised and local partners' tactics for addressing them. Third, we review the lasting innovations expected from the experiments.

3.1. Local actors' understandings of the European Green Deal

SHARED GREEN DEAL was framed as a project to support local actions towards the goals of the European Green Deal. Some local partners referenced this policy in their applications, monthly meetings, or post-experiment reflections, although these mentions were few. One local experiment (Sustainable Food – Sweden) stated that their goal was to translate the Farm to Fork strategy (the European Green Deal's food sector strategy) for the local context and use local context to inform how the strategy should be implemented in the EU. Some local partners referred to the European Green Deal and related policies in their applications to demonstrate readiness to take part in the project or the need for the project in their location (e.g. Efficient Renovations – Spain, Sustainable Food – Slovakia, Clean Energy – Poland). Others viewed the European Green Deal as a form of support for their work (e.g. Clean Energy – Spain); a benchmark for success (e.g. Circular Economy – Portugal); a source of legal regulation (e.g. Sustainable Mobility – Bulgaria, Sustainable Mobility – Lithuania); or a source of funding that policy and business actors are interested in, discussing, or actively using (e.g. Efficient Renovations – Spain). A few mentioned the fact that some important local actors resist or reject the European Green Deal (i.e. farmers, anti-EU national or local governments) (Sustainable Food – Slovakia). One interpreted the policy's messages as having the potential to raise “*fear*” among participants, which would have been counterproductive if mentioned in an otherwise constructive and positive experiment (Preserving Biodiversity – Slovenia).

Rather than referring directly to the European Green Deal, in most cases, local partners framed their work according to specific local challenges and goals that are in line with this EU policy. We identified seven categories of problem framings.⁴

⁴ In compiling these, we referred exclusively to the core problems and goals of each experiment as identified by the local partner. Local partners mentioned several other challenges throughout the course of the project, but for the purposes of this analysis we were primarily interested in how they understood the central challenges and goals of their social experiments.

Environmental and health conditions

All 24 local partners mentioned poor environmental and/or health conditions – existing, actively deteriorating, or predicted – as the foundational challenge that they wanted to address with their social experiments. This included some organisations’ desire or obligation to meet climate and/or conservation targets.

Lack of education and awareness

This problem framing refers to the absence of awareness, knowledge, or information among key groups about certain sustainability challenges or solutions. For example, in Biodiversity – Ireland, the local partner stated that residents reported being uninformed about biodiversity and how to improve it; the partner viewed education as an important way to enhance the preservation of nature. This problem framing was mentioned by 10 organisations (Circular Economy – 1, Efficient Renovations – 2, Sustainable Mobility – 1, Sustainable Food – 2, Preserving Biodiversity – 4).

Economic unsustainability of environmentally friendly options

This problem framing refers to the fact that in some sectors and locations, environmentally friendly options are not economically viable. For example, in Sustainable Economy – France, the local partner stated that environmentally sustainable clothing mechanisms (local second-hand stores and waste recovery centres) are not economically sustainable and face competition from unsustainable alternatives. Overall, this was mentioned by eight organisations (Clean Energy – 2, Circular Economy – 1, Efficient Renovations – 3, Sustainable Food – 1, Preserving Biodiversity – 1). Many organisations framed this specifically in relation to those in economically or socially vulnerable positions (five organisations (Clean Energy – 1, Efficient Renovations – 3, Preserving Biodiversity – 1)). For example, in Efficient Renovations – Hungary, the local organisation wanted to address the fact that public renovations financing was not accessible for those in rural energy poverty – the population that could most benefit from it.

Unsustainable social practices or individual behaviour

This problem framing identified shared practices or individual behaviours that are considered harmful to the environment, safety, or health as the central problem. Many local partners noted the lack of infrastructure available to improve these as a complementary reason for this problem. For example, in Sustainable Mobility – Bulgaria, the local partner stated that students were dependent on cars for transport to school and that many did not have access to sustainable alternatives. This framing was mentioned by eight organisations (Circular Economy – 3, Efficient Renovations – 1, Sustainable Mobility – 4).

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Lack of inclusion and participation

Some framed their main problem as the absence of key groups in decision-making, policy, planning, or action on sustainability challenges. This was referred to in both formal contexts, such as the lack of participatory mechanisms in policymaking, and informal ones, such as certain groups' perceived lack of interest in engaging in a topic. For example, in Clean Energy – Poland, the local partner identified that residents and women had not been invited to meaningfully take part in planning the transition away from coal. This type of framing was mentioned by six local partners (Clean Energy – 4, Sustainable Mobility – 1, Sustainable Food – 1).

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Disconnected actors

Some organisations stated that to solve certain sustainability challenges, actors that hold different types of expertise or serve different functions in a community must be connected. For example, in Sustainable Food – Slovakia, the local partner had identified that there was no existing local network that connects actors in the food system to work for a more sustainable supply chain. This framing was mentioned by six organisations (Circular Economy – 2, Efficient Renovations – 1, Sustainable Food – 3).

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Policy gaps

This problem framing identifies where national, regional, and/or local policy does not specifically or sufficiently address a sustainability challenge. For example, in Sustainable Food – Sweden, the local partner found that national food policy was unable to improve outcomes for the country's population, in large part because it did not consider the behavioural, social, and cultural dimensions of food. This framing was mentioned by three organisations (Sustainable Mobility – 1, Sustainable Food – 2).

3.2. Types of governance innovations and outcomes

3.2.1. Governance innovations

Figure 3.2. Typology of governance innovations

We identified four types of governance innovations across the social experiments: education, relational, organisational, and policy inclusion innovations (Figure 3.2).

Education innovations

Education innovations are activities that change the ways in which people learn about sustainability challenges and solutions. We identified these types of innovations in five experiment streams: Community visioning for clean energy, Local accelerator hubs for circular economy, Knowledge networks for efficient renovations, Sustainable school mobility labs, and Biodiversity study circles. Examples of activities undertaken as part of these innovations include learning experiences, workshops (creative arts; planning/discussing; interactive), collecting good practices, creating an online platform for networking and knowledge exchange, and games.

“ I am convinced that the way [study circles] are conducted (the participants co-create the learning content and know from the first beginning that we will also have to implement the action goal / final event for public) all involved want to take away from it something positive, meaningful, and useful for themselves and show or do the same for community.”

[Preserving Biodiversity, Slovenia, Local Partner, #DS4]

Immediate outcomes of these innovations included: new knowledge about content or new skills that were shared with family, friends and neighbours, other organisations, and other locations (including through promotion efforts such as events, flyers, videos, etc.); positive feelings of increased confidence, having been listened to, and connection with others; and actions such as deciding to undertake renovations (Efficient Renovations – Lithuania), changing plans for how to undertake renovations, obtaining national funding for more renovations (Efficient Renovations – Ireland), and forming a second round of study circles (Preserving Biodiversity – Ireland and Slovenia).

Box 3.2a. Governance innovations in Louisburgh, Ireland (Efficient Renovations)

Photo: Climate Action Louisburgh Locality

BEFORE ●

Climate Action Louisburgh Locality (CALL), a non-governmental organisation supported by Mayo County Council in Ireland, sought to increase the number of retrofitted homes in their area through raising awareness about the benefits and ease of renovations, identified as a key barrier to renovations there.

DURING ●

CALL brought together a renovations knowledge network with residents and professionals. They toured homes that were soon to be renovated and those that had already been renovated to learn about the realities of renovations, focusing on the restoration and conservation of older homes. They recorded some of the tours and put them on their website as an enduring resource.

AFTER ●

Residents gained practical knowledge about how to undertake renovations and about their benefits. They developed relationships with each other and enhanced networking with professionals. CALL plans to keep the network alive, continuing to share information and practical knowledge about renovations through this group with the goal of reaching others who are interested in undertaking them.

Relational innovations

Relational innovations are activities that reconfigure relationships, such as by connecting actors within or across sectors who were previously disconnected. We identified these types of innovations in five experiment streams: Community visioning for clean energy, Local accelerator hubs for circular economy, Knowledge networks for efficient renovations, Food transition assemblies, and Biodiversity study circles. Examples of activities undertaken as part of these innovations include workshops (creative arts; planning/discussing; interactive), creating an online platform for networking and knowledge exchange, and learning experiences.

“Participants became more interactive and friendly because of the engagement created during working groups. Some of them, especially the local administrator, were surprised about the methodology and how this was effective in creating involvement between participants.”

[Sustainable Food, Italy, Local Partner, #DS2]

Immediate outcomes of these innovations included: improved networking, collaboration, and communication; positive feelings of increased confidence, having been listened to, and connection with others; and actions such as local partners pledging continued support for members who wanted the experiment activities to continue, incorporating the lessons learned from the experiment into political advocacy (Efficient Renovations – Hungary), and maintaining the experiment with modifications to make it more feasible (Efficient Renovations – Ireland, Lithuania, Spain).

“[W]hat is interesting is that the group are knowing each other also better. For example, [the] “recycle centre” (...), now they have relations[h]ips (...) [T]hey have succeed[ed] (...) in this case in creating a prototype of [a] catalogue of services they can propose in common.”

[Circular Economy, France, Local Partner, #DS3]

Organisational innovations

Organisational innovations are activities that rearrange organisational structures or enhance the capacity of actors. We identified these innovations in all experiment streams in how local partners learned about how to undertake social experiments (Evans et al., 2021):

“[I]f this kind of opportunity to participate in [a] similar initiative will arise in the future, we would be very keen to participate again, because we found it very useful not only for our knowledge network members, but also for [our] organisation too. (...) we grew within in terms of our activities, we made new connections and had very positive feedback from our members.”

[Efficient Renovations, Lithuania, Local Partner, #DS4]

We also identified organisational innovations in relation to the wider sectors in the following three experiments: Community visioning for clean energy, Local accelerator hubs for circular economy, and Food transition assemblies. Examples of activities undertaken as part of these innovations include workshops (capacity building; interactive), creating an online platform for networking and knowledge exchange, and collecting information from participants and/or the public (surveys, questionnaires, interviews, etc.).

“(…) [P]eople/institutions already involved in some energy communities got to know each other (some already knew others, but all learnt about other initiatives), and people not yet involved got to know us and these already ongoing initiatives (…) and even without the participation of the provincial government we see that they are already sharing information, worries, and possible solutions among them and with us as well.”

[Clean Energy, Spain, Local Partner, #DS4]

Immediate outcomes of these innovations included proposals, recommendations, visions, and narratives for addressing the European Green Deal sustainability challenges at the local level. For example, in one experiment participants developed a concrete action plan for moving forward and connecting with similar organisations in other locations to spread the process (Sustainable Food – Netherlands). In others, organisations applied for additional funding for follow-up projects (Circular Economy – Slovenia, Sustainable Food – Italy).

Policy inclusion innovations

Policy inclusion innovations are activities that seek to change how actors contribute to formal policymaking (both in government institutions and in other types of institutions such as schools) or to include new actors. We identified these in three experiment streams: Community visioning for clean energy, Sustainable school mobility labs, and Food transition assemblies. Examples of activities undertaken as part of these innovations include workshops (planning/discussion; interactive), planning/presenting/implementing recommendations, and collecting information from participants and/or the public (surveys, questionnaires, interviews, etc.).

“For us, it was a new experience to work with schoolchildren, teachers and specialists representing different institutions in one group. It was a challenge to make them work (…) in the same direction knowing they have different background[s] and different understanding[s] (…) We were trying to find methods to work these different groups together, trying to understand each other and looking for possible common solutions on the topic.”

[Sustainable Mobility, Lithuania, Local Partner, #DS4]

Immediate outcomes included positive feelings of increased confidence, having been listened to, and connection with others; proposals, recommendations, visions, and narratives for addressing the European Green Deal sustainability challenges at the local level; and actions such as implementing recommendations to improve school infrastructure for pedestrians, bicycles and buses (Sustainable Mobility – Portugal).

Box 3.2b. Governance innovations in Stockholm, Sweden (Sustainable Food)

Photo: REFORMATEN

BEFORE

REFORMATEN, the non-governmental organisation that ran the food transition assemblies in Stockholm, Sweden, identified their key challenge as a policy gap – Sweden’s food policy did not take the behavioural, social, and cultural aspects of food into account and therefore was unable to improve health outcomes equally across Stockholm’s diverse population.

DURING

They conducted a series of food transition assemblies in which they brought together actors from across the food system to envision and plan for a different future, using interactive and creative arts workshop methods. They shared several meals together, as well.

AFTER

The assemblies resulted in a food policy brief, containing the participants’ shared vision and nine action points, for use in advocacy towards a healthier, more sustainable, and equitable food policy. REFORMATEN was also invited to take part in a national working group on these issues.

See Appendix A2, Table A2.2 for an overview of governance innovations in all experiment streams.

3.2.2. Governance tensions and tactics

Our analysis identified some governance tensions, or challenges, and tactics, or strategies used to address these, that arose during the making of the social experiments (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014; Manganelli, 2024a; Manganelli, 2024b). Here, we focus on those related to the relationships, power dynamics, and politics in the experiments and present three examples of tensions and corresponding tactics in the experimental governance of the European Green Deal through SHARED GREEN DEAL.⁵

⁵ This list is not exhaustive but meant to provide a snapshot of some of the tensions and tactics that arose in multiple experiments.

Tension 1: Recruitment and attendance

Finding participants for uncertain processes that required a time investment was a challenge for most organisations, and some had to decide whether to recruit larger or more diverse groups that may have been less interested in the topic versus smaller, more homogenous but committed groups. In some experiments, stakeholder groups deemed important were not recruited or did not participate and thus were not represented. Some potential participants did not want to take part because they believed that the process would not have benefits or that other actors were responsible for resolving the issue. Most also had difficulties securing attendance, dealing with logistics to make it manageable for participants, and managing the high volume of communication required.

Tactic: Aligning actors

In recruitment, some local partners put significant effort into crafting messaging that resonated with their target participants, identifying communications channels that reached them, and leveraging existing networks and relationships. They demonstrated through their messaging and the experiment activities themselves the value of bringing participants with different backgrounds but shared values together, finding ways for them to identify common goals, communicate with each other, and collaborate on the same activities.

Tension 2: Interpersonal dynamics

To carry out the experiments, local partners had to form relationships and build trust with participants of various types (residents, business, policy, etc.), facilitators and community intermediaries, government offices and institutions, and non-governmental or community organisations. These actors had different interests: some experiments faced a lack of support from key actors that affected their progression, and finding common ground between stakeholders was not always easy. The experiments sometimes put strain on personal relationships. A specific sub-set of this tension is challenges with facilitation and participation during the experiment activities, including mitigating power dynamics, ensuring those with different participation styles were included, getting participants to think in a new way, or dealing with low levels of engagement. Organisers and facilitators also faced the risk of unintentionally raising participants' expectations about what was feasible through the experiment, which made it difficult to secure meaningful participation in some cases due to a lack of trust.

Tactic: Sustaining engagement

Many local partners put significant time and effort into building or rebuilding relationships and trust with and between actors. They also sought to make the schedule and location manageable for participants, fostered a welcoming atmosphere at the events (i.e. with informal activities, collaborative creative arts, or shared meals), and ensured those with different participation styles had a way to contribute, in many cases relying upon external expertise in facilitation to advise on the best way to do so. Some maintained clear, regular communication with participants and other actors during and after the experiments to ensure that expectations were managed. Some local partners also gave participants ownership over the experiment, asking for and incorporating their feedback, giving them roles as experts or coordinators, or providing them opportunities to take initiative and responsibility.

Tension 3: Institutional barriers

Some experiments challenged entrenched cultures or came up against risk aversion in institutions. In some cases, scheduling and permissions (e.g. for schoolchildren to participate in the activities) raised problems for starting the experiments. In some locations, uncertainty around elections or political processes also caused delays.

Tactic: Developing a supportive environment

Flexibility and adaptation were key skills utilised by all local partners as they navigated unexpected developments and responded to changing circumstances and feedback, modifying their original plans, sometimes multiple times. Some embedded experiments in existing programming, creating connections with other projects, international networks, or national/regional/local policy frameworks. Others attempted to formally link the experiment to ongoing government processes that could have an impact. Some formed connections with other initiatives that have similar aims and/or partnered with community members, intermediaries, and facilitators that offered local knowledge, expertise, or connections. When initial attempts at this failed, some local partners had to consider new strategies and take different approaches.

3.3. Approaches to public engagement at the local level: main shifts and expectations beyond the experiment

3.3.1. Shifting approaches to public engagement

Although all experiments resulted in changes that are expected to be long-lasting, such as increased awareness or better-connected networks, some experiments were more effectively embedded in existing governance systems than others, indicating they are more likely to have continued influence after the experiment period, be successfully transferred to other settings, or have cumulative impacts in conjunction with other activities (Sengers et al., 2021).⁶ In this section, we focus on governance innovations which, by the end of the experiment, had begun to transform into longer-term changes to education, relationships, organisational structures, or policy inclusion. We have divided them by type of innovation based on their primary function while recognising that many innovations represent multiple types of innovations simultaneously.

Education innovations

- **Preserving Biodiversity – Greece:** In collaboration with the botanical garden of the Syngros Urban Forest in Amaroussion, Athens, Greece, study circle participants labelled the garden's endemic plants with information that will help visitors, including schoolchildren who frequently take field trips there, learn about the plant species native to this region. The local partner found that the study circle, a social activity which connected the municipality with citizens, was a valuable addition to their work and hoped to continue it.
- **Preserving Biodiversity – Slovenia:** Participants in Tolmin's biodiversity study circle, which focused on birds, developed an outdoor classroom in a community garden. Following the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment, a second study circle, financed by national funding, investigated community gardens to facilitate the long-term upkeep and use of this outdoor classroom as a community resource.

Relational innovations

- **Clean Energy – Spain:** The social experiment demonstrated the benefits of building relationships when conducting informational and organisational meetings about energy

⁶ Some experiments were designed to become long-term (e.g. knowledge networks) or be repeated (e.g. study circles), whereas others were time bound with the potential for follow-up on the results (e.g. food assemblies, community visioning, local accelerator hubs, mobility labs). Some local partners expressed intentions to replicate the experiment or a version of it in another location.

communities, as well as the importance of collecting more detailed information from people interested in joining or starting energy communities. The local partner is using these insights in a new energy community support office financed by the national government.

- **Circular Economy – Portugal:** Although a participant in Santo Tirso’s social experiment had the idea to utilise waste from one sector in support of another sector prior to joining the local accelerator hub, *“the social experiment allowed for this specific participant to create the necessary network and knowledge to further develop the idea”* [Circular Economy, Portugal, Local Partner, #DS4]. After meeting other members of the hub who could be direct partners in this circular solution, the participant began laboratory testing on the feasibility of the proposal.

Organisational innovations

- **Clean Energy – the United Kingdom:** The social experiment launched a platform to bring different sectors together to address the challenge of healthy homes in Jaywick. This is being continued in a new energy hub, an idea that arose directly from the experiment, which is run with community support. Existing funding and resources are being used more effectively and the hub has attracted additional financing from national and other sources.
- **Circular Economy – France:** Val-de-Marne has a new tailoring and textile repair service as a result of the design thinking business innovation methods used in SHARED GREEN DEAL. With additional sponsorship secured from a fund in France, Retoucherie EF94 has helped make it easier for people living in this municipality to have their garments repaired, extending their life, keeping textiles out of landfill, reducing the production of clothing, and generating income – all while facilitating relationships and positive social interactions in the neighbourhood.

Policy inclusion innovations

- **Sustainable Mobility – Bulgaria:** A student’s idea to construct and decorate ‘mailboxes’ for schoolchildren to share their thoughts, ideas, and suggestions about sustainable mobility in Sofia was implemented and shared with other schools in the experiment’s final exhibition. Schools viewed it as a promising communication mechanism to gather student input on other topics:

“We were assured by the schools that they will continue to use the post boxes as a communication channel between students, teachers and school administration and this will be a local solution provided by the project that solves the problem of lack of communication on many topics that students are interested in.” [Sustainable Mobility, Bulgaria, Local Partner, #DS4]

- **Sustainable Mobility – Portugal:** The municipality of Braga stated that the mobility lab and the methods used within it brought about *“changes in governance practices”* and *“a new way of approaching and solving mobility-related problems”* [Sustainable Mobility, Portugal, Local Partner, #DS4]. The experiment recommendations led to specific infrastructure changes around some schools, such as a new pedestrian crossing. The municipality also created a programme to help children learn how to ride bicycles, which they discovered many did not know how to do. They planned to replicate the methodology in other schools that expressed interest in continuing the project.

Box 3.3a. How social experiments lead to change: three examples from SHARED GREEN DEAL

SOCIAL EXPERIMENT	BEFORE	DURING	AFTER
Sustainable Mobility BULGARIA	<p>Unsustainable social practices or individual behaviours: Despite high levels of air pollution, many students are dependent on cars to travel to school. Better understanding of students' mobility habits and the potential ways to change these (behaviour/practice change; new school or city measures) can help improve the environment and health.</p>	<p>Sustainable school mobility lab: Experiment activities focused on education and policy inclusion innovations brought children and the wider community from three schools together in engaging workshops where they discussed their mobility habits and potential solutions, worked on creative art projects, engaged in learning experiences, and identified/presented recommendations for improving sustainable transportation to school.</p>	<p>Policy inclusion - communication mechanism: In their creative arts workshops, students came up with the idea for a mailbox to collect stories and ideas about sustainable school mobility. They made the mailboxes together and placed them in the schools. These were seen as an excellent way for students to communicate on other topics as well and schools planned to continue using them beyond the experiment.</p>
Preserving Biodiversity GREECE	<p>Lack of education and awareness: Urban development threatens the environment and human health in this Athens suburb. However, residents are not informed about these challenges or the benefits of urban biodiversity conservation and restoration, and they lack a shared vision.</p>	<p>Study circle: Experiment activities focused on educational and relational innovations brought residents together to direct their own experiential learning about the urban biodiversity around them, focusing on pollinators (i.e. bees) and indigenous plants.</p>	<p>Educational service: Participants collaborated with the local botanical garden to leave something behind for the wider community: labels for the indigenous plants in the garden that will help educate visitors and promote awareness of the region's unique natural environment.</p>
Circular Economy PORTUGAL	<p>Disconnected actors: Previous efforts to link the city's main sectors (textiles, agri-food, and plastics) and educate about circular solutions were insufficient and renewed, innovative efforts were needed to bring people together, raise awareness, and drive innovation.</p>	<p>Local accelerator hub: Experiment activities focused on relational and organisational innovations and brought professionals from the city's main sectors together to network and identify synergies through interactive, design thinking workshops.</p>	<p>Networking facilitates technical solution: The workshops connected actors from different sectors and led to the launch of testing of a circular economy solution to use waste (sludge) from one sector as a useful input (fertiliser) in another sector.</p>

Photo: Sofia Development Association

Photo: Municipality of Amaroussian

Photo: Municipality of Santo Tirso

3.3.2. Limitations

Despite these promising developments, some structural features of the project affected the experiments' potential long-term development in some cases. These included:

- Funding and resources for follow-up programmes (in some locations more funding for the continuation or further development of the experiments was difficult to access; continuing to invest the amount of time needed for upkeep after the experiment ended was also infeasible for some partners);
- The limited duration of the experiment (insufficient time to build trust or commitment in some locations); and
- The embeddedness of the experiments in the existing social/community infrastructure, including connections with policy and government decision-makers (in some locations, the lack of engagement by these actors or unsupportive policies meant that once the experiment finished the partner changed their approach or returned to their previous work approaches).

One limitation of this analysis is that data collection typically ended within six months of the social experiments finishing, so there is limited information about long-term change for the majority of cases. It is still valuable to look at the status of the experiments upon completion and in their immediate aftermath: due to the one-year timeframe of the project, it is possible to see how such interventions might shift approaches to public engagement over a longer timescale.

Box 3.3b. What makes experimental governance of the European Green Deal work

Frame the problem.

- ✓ Contextualise the European Green Deal in the reality of local challenges and resources, rooted in a deep understanding of the situation.
- ✓ Address social challenges to also address technological, environmental, or climate change ones.

Implement creative but intentional governance innovations.

- ✓ Connect the problem framing to the experimental activities undertaken.
- ✓ Do something new or creative with participants.
- ✓ Use concrete activities, such as learning experiences.
- ✓ Set clear expectations about what uncertainty means for the experiment's outcomes.
- ✓ Meet unexpected developments with flexibility and reflection.
- ✓ Give participants a degree of ownership or decision-making power.
- ✓ Involve organisers, facilitators, and participants that can help achieve the goals of the experiment.
- ✓ Focus on building relationships.

Embed the experiment in existing governance.

- ✓ Integrate the experiment into institutions and programmes from the outset.
- ✓ Make strategic partnerships with actors and institutions that can enable success.
- ✓ Embrace incremental progress as well as transformation.

Rely on trusted support.

- ✓ Join a network of experimenters and exchange experiences.
- ✓ Work with co-creators (i.e. academic researchers, practical experts, peer experimenters) that can push the experiments forward and help solve problems.

3.4. Conclusion

In this section, we have shown how the local partners in the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments framed the European Green Deal in the context of the challenges they face locally and addressed them through specific governance innovations. Through new forms of education, relationship building, organisational configurations, and policy inclusion, the local partners were able to probe and address key obstacles to the European Green Deal, such as a lack of awareness and education, economic feasibility, unsustainable social practices and behaviours, lack of inclusion and participation, disconnected actors, and policy gaps. Despite some important limitations, many social experiments formed the basis of expected long-term, meaningful change in the ways that institutions and organisations work to address energy, waste, building renovations, transportation, food systems, and the natural environment. In the next section, we summarise some of the key lessons from these social experiments and provide recommendations for those involved in climate governance.

4. Learning points and recommendations for policy and governance

4.1. SHARED GREEN DEAL's contributions to experimental governance

Through governance innovations in education, relationships, organisations, and policy inclusion, SHARED GREEN DEAL's experiments contributed to the learning, change in behaviour or social practices, and collaboration that form an important part of the everyday practice of climate governance. In some cases, they also led to important longer-term developments that alter the way these challenges are governed at the local level, through actions taken by local authorities, non-governmental organisations, communities, and businesses.

Since the project was framed around the European Green Deal, it is not surprising that the social experiments mostly sought to improve existing efforts in line with this policy (i.e. national or local climate plans or the vision statements of organisations) rather than to redefine goals or radically change approaches (Sengers et al., 2021). However, this is promising considering that plans for addressing climate change are often considered ambitious but their implementation lacking (Dubash, 2020; Tørstad et al., 2025).

Local partners and participants appreciated the experiments for several reasons. They were able to: participate in something new ('experimenting'; using new or creative methods); talk about topics that were important to participants but marginalised in public discussion or topics on which they had few opportunities to exchange with like-minded people; listen to new perspectives; feel included in a group and be heard by those in power; create new relationships and connections; learn new and useful things, gain experience, or deepen their understanding of how certain processes work; show what is possible; demonstrate the value of the initiatives and their outcomes; promote their work or expand their market (especially for business and professional partners); build capacity for working on an EU project (especially for local partners running the experiments); and have an enjoyable experience. Many local partners did not expect participants to be as enthusiastic and interested in the topics or as willing to take part in the social experiments as they were, demonstrating both the potential and need for experimental approaches.

A key benefit of SHARED GREEN DEAL was not just that the project enabled action on European Green Deal challenges, but that it also included several points of observation and reflection (Ehnert, 2023). This approach proved beneficial for longer-term institutional and organisational learning, as local partners built their own internal capacity through the activities, regular reflection, and the collection of participant feedback (Evans et al., 2021).

4.2. Learning points for experimental governance

As this report has shown, however, the social experiments were not always straightforward, and their impact not guaranteed. Some local partners found the social experiments challenging to maintain once the project ended. Some attributed this in part to their duration: they considered it too short to create a meaningful collective process or realise the proposed ideas. Others cited insufficient funding and resources for continuing and proposed that such experiments should be connected to longer-term funding programmes. One organisation mentioned that the amount of funding the project provided was not commensurate with the scale and degree of sustainability challenges faced. Another issue was maintaining trust with participants once the experiment ended. Local partners had high demands on their time and resources during this project, including for project management. They also had to follow the project guidelines while also managing the flexibility and responsibility they had for implementing their own unique experiment, oftentimes doing something they had never done before.

There were further challenges to the long-term impact of the social experiments. Some local partners noted that the sectors they were working in are difficult to change and may have powerful interests behind them (e.g. energy). There are practical barriers to change in some areas as well (e.g. promoting bike riding when many students live too far away from school to do so or infrastructure is not in place). Policy actors at different scales were often viewed as a barrier to long-term “living” of the social experiments, among which local partners noted a lack of prioritisation of these issues or resistance to change on these issues. In those experiments that delivered policy recommendations, organisations found that although such recommendations can be made, they may not be taken up immediately or ever. Some participants still felt they lacked a voice at the policy level at the end of the experiments, or that policy was not receptive to their voices. In some locations, the experiments highlighted a need for supportive national or local regulations or policies for the social experiment to have a substantial or longer-term impact.

4.3. Recommendations

In this section, we propose recommendations for policymakers, researchers, and funding bodies based on the results of this analysis. These recommendations are aimed at highlighting the importance of experimental governance and social experimental approaches, as well as improving the ways in which these are undertaken.

4.3.1. Recommendations for policy

European Union policymakers

- 1. Identify and share the local and diverse ways in which the European Green Deal is already being interpreted and implemented.**
- 2. Publicly recognise the role of local social experiments in achieving the European Green Deal and use them to inform understandings of this policy framework at the EU level.**
- 3. Identify additional ways to incorporate support for local efforts to govern the European Green Deal into policy, research, and funding,** such as ensuring that new EU Missions and Climate Contracts integrate social experimentation as a core delivery method.

4. **Work with local experimenters to create a social experiment support body** that can advise them on methods and activities, facilitate the sharing of best practices, and help them work through unexpected developments and challenges.

National, local, and regional policymakers, general

1. **Demonstrate support for social experiments and similar initiatives** by leading them, taking part in them, supporting their outcomes, or implementing policies and regulations that facilitate their work. This can help build longer-term trust with constituents and key partner organisations, as well as improve internal communications within institutions such as local authorities.

National, local, and regional policymakers, running social experiments

1. **Embed social experiments in ongoing processes** and ensure they can continue or be built upon after the ‘experiment’ ends. Consider this deeply at the beginning of an experiment and monitor/adapt plans to do so throughout.
2. **Engage in the conflicts, diversity of perspectives, and relationship dynamics of social experiments** rather than focusing exclusively on effective project management.
3. **Co-create unique local social experiments with local and community-based actors** based on proven methodologies to multiply the successes of experimental governance across contexts.
4. **Create internal structures or processes for collecting, retaining, and sharing learning from experimental processes** to aid governance transformation.
5. **Join networks of social experimenters** to exchange experiences with peers and enhance the cohesion of the collective movement towards experimental governance of the European Green Deal.

4.3.2. Recommendations for research

1. **Ensure that research efforts to engage in social experiments consider the ways in which these experiments are part of larger processes of experimental governance.** Address the tensions between the necessary project-based framings of research and the real long-term needs of localities in response to climate change by helping partners find creative ways to embed experiments in these processes, considering sustainability challenges holistically.
2. **In co-creating social experiments with local actors, become comfortable relinquishing control and power to partners but maintain a high level of support.** Social experiments initiated by researchers should emphasise the centrality of achieving the local actors’ sustainability goals and take account of the existing governance processes in their locations. Determine what skills, experience, and knowledge the research team is best poised to provide and calibrate how much support the partner needs. This is best done through ongoing dialogue and flexible adaptation to the extent possible.

4.3.3. Recommendations for funding

1. **Finance local projects.** Initiatives at the local level can have a demonstrable and meaningful effect on governance. Donors should consider where their funding could have the greatest impact, not just on the level of establishment and experience of the grantee or low financial risk.

2. **Ensure sustainable experimentation.** Financing and resources for experiments do not need to be massive to make a difference but must be sustainable. This could mean that funding should be long-term, but also that funding should be directed towards organisations that can use it to leverage other funds or find new ways to utilise existing sources of funding. Funding bodies should consider how to work with partners to identify and take advantage of these opportunities throughout the course of projects.
3. **Consider diverse measures of success for projects,** as experiments may progress in unexpected ways and result in surprising outcomes that may nevertheless be beneficial for both donor and grantee goals.

As the results from SHARED GREEN DEAL have shown, social experiments can be an important aspect of experimental governance of the European Green Deal. It is crucial that they are carefully designed based on the lessons of projects such as this one, coordinated with other governance mechanisms, and include moments of evaluation to ensure their impact. To achieve the ambitions of this policy, social experiments should be included in all the EU's climate governance funding streams.

5. Conclusions

This report analysed how SHARED GREEN DEAL's 24 social experiments have contributed to the experimental governance of the European Green Deal at the local level. Overall, the report finds that social experimentation can enable local actors to govern the European Green Deal in a way that pays attention to the tensions and politics inherent to governance in relation to climate change. However, to do so effectively and long-term, actors must embed social experiments in ongoing governance processes and funding streams, devote significant time to relationship building, and successfully navigate unexpected developments. This report has also made recommendations for how policy, research, and funding can work with social experiments to improve the experimental governance of the European Green Deal.

These findings capture the outcomes of the experiments at a specific moment in time, and we anticipate that the ways in which they contribute to experimental governance will continue to evolve. The experiment implementation and data collection period was approximately 12 months and, in most cases, there was no opportunity to follow-up with local partners, so this report cannot fully assess experiments' long-lasting impact. The experiments will result in many unintended, untracked impacts that the researchers or the local partners may never know about (Rossitto, 2021). Furthermore, experiments, once launched, are never really over. They continue to inform the work of those who take part in them in multiple ways: "transformation is not here an endpoint... but rather is already present in the politics and practice of governing by experiment" (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 237).

Our report has several implications for the governance of sustainability transitions. Policies that exist at supra-national and national level need to be 'scaled down' – or made actionable at regional and local levels – and social experimentation is one way to do this. SHARED GREEN DEAL demonstrates the value of a network of experiments implementing shared methods simultaneously, and how co-creative design can adapt these methods to different contexts. This reinforces the importance of local context in experiments as well as the value of supportive networks of experimenters. Building upon the work of SHARED GREEN DEAL, further investigation is needed to understand how to coordinate and connect such experiments across regions, countries, Europe, and the world to enhance collaboration, collective impact, and effectiveness (Meyer, 2023; Sengers et al., 2021).

Experiments have often been characterised as 'projects' that lend themselves to short-term thinking, low ambition, and incremental change (Torrens and von Wirth, 2021) and can be "reduced to a matter of efficiently managing stakeholders and socio-technical innovations" (Sierhuis et al., 2024, p. 304). Instead, our experiences with SHARED GREEN DEAL show that those undertaking experiments can benefit from embracing the uncertain nature of experiments and channelling the diverse and conflicting perspectives of participants to "foster change" (Sierhuis et al., 2024, p. 304). Many of our experiments found value in the areas where they 'failed' to meet their goals or address the challenges they hoped to (Exner and Strüver, 2023). This is also a mindset change that is needed for climate action. Our analysis shows that the social experiment, with its focus on learning, relationships, and networks, is an approach that can help ensure that experimentation is not a waste of money or time but can make an important contribution even when it 'fails' by traditional measures (Manganelli, 2024a). Furthermore, our results suggest that although large investments are required to carry out holistic sustainability plans that have transformative impact, without small amounts

of funding for social experiments that help reconfigure social infrastructure, perhaps this funding will be used improperly or will not be able to have its intended effect.

A deeper analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL data presented in this report could seek to better understand the simultaneous and overlapping roles played by multiple scales of governance in implementing climate policies (Meyer, 2023). This includes a more nuanced understanding of how the experiments became embedded in governance structures and led to long-term change (Ehnert, 2023; Sengers et al., 2021), of the political tensions and tactics of governing by experiment, and the ways in which experiments ‘failed’ to achieve their goals (Exner and Strüver, 2023; Manganelli, 2024a; Manganelli, 2024b). It could also further explore the different outcomes of those social experiments run by local authorities and those run by non-governmental organisations to better understand whether any patterns that emerge and the implications for future experimentation (Haderer, 2023; Manganelli, 2024a). Experimental governance forms just part of the long-term transformation required for achieving the goals of the European Green Deal (Ehnert, 2023). However, the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments show that it can be a crucial part of this transformation. Through flexible and reflexive governance innovations that address the social aspects of key Green Deal challenges in addition to the technical ones, we can better support the behavioural, social, and cultural change required for climate action.

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Appendix A1. Methods

A1.1. Introduction

The objective of the SHARED GREEN DEAL analysis theme ‘Governance agendas, framings, and conventions’ was to examine the framing and governance of the European Green Deal at the local scale through the lens of the six SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiment streams. As the data collected covers the experiment period and its immediate aftermath, the analysis focused on the “making” of the experiments in Bulkeley, Castán Broto and Edwards’ (2014) analytical framework on urban climate change experiments, which includes four interdependent areas: problematisation (formulating a problem), alignment of actors and interests, rendering a problem technical (identifying the field of intervention), and rendering it compelling for actors to address (p. 45). However, we also sought to identify aspects of the “maintaining” and “living” of experiments – how these experiments continued and/or became embedded in the daily life of the localities where they were undertaken. We used data sources that primarily focus on the perspectives of the local partners who ran the experiments, including participant observation collected in monthly surveys and meeting notes and written reflections at the end of the experiments. We analysed the data qualitatively through a thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2023), first identifying excerpts related to governance in the data itself and then mapping these onto the framework from Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards (2014).

A1.2. Context and data sources

Table A1.2a: Social experiments profiles

#	Priority area (thematic stream)	Approach	Target group	Place of social experiment	Local partner organisation	Context (rural/urban)*
1	Clean Energy	Community visioning	Policymakers, businesses, local communities	Granada, Spain	Local authority (Diputación de Granada)	mix
				Bełchatów, Poland	NGO (Polish Green Network)	mix
				Jaywick, UK	Local authority (Essex County Council)	rural
				Ærø, Marstal, Denmark	NGO (Fonden Motorfabrikken Marstal and Blue Innovators)	rural
2	Circular Economy	Local accelerator hubs	Local businesses, academics, authorities, and NGOs	Santo Tirso, Portugal	Local authority (Municipality of Santo Tirso)	urban
				Val-de-Marne, France	NGO (Val de Marne en Transition)	urban
				Nicosia/Limassol/Larnaca, Cyprus	National authority (Cyprus Organization for Standardization)	mix
				Ljubljana, Slovenia	Local authority (Technology Park Ljubljana)	urban
3	Efficient Renovations	Knowledge networks on energy renovation and eco-home-tours	Under-represented and marginalised groups and renovation professionals (40-60% women)	Zaragoza, Spain	NGO (ECODES Zaragoza)	urban
				Nógrád County, Hungary	NGO (Habitat for Humanity Hungary)	rural
				Vilnius, Lithuania	Local authority (Let's Renovate the City Vilnius)	urban
				Louisburgh, Mayo County, Ireland	Regional authority (Mayo County Council Louisburgh)	rural
4	Sustainable Mobility	School mobility labs	Per experiment 30 young people (aged 10-16) and 5 to 10 stakeholders such as teachers, parents, and school administrators	Braga, Portugal	Local authority (Municipality of Braga)	urban
				Galway, Ireland	NGO (Am Meitheal Rothar Ireland)	urban
				Panevėžys, Lithuania	NGO (ECAT Lithuania)	urban
				Sofia, Bulgaria	NGO (Sofia Development Association Bulgaria)	urban
5	Sustainable Food	Local food Assemblies	Young people aged 18-35 years	Stockholm, Sweden	NGO (REFORMATEN)	urban
				Cella Monte, Italy	NGO (ASFODELO)	rural
				Košice, Slovakia	NGO (Klíma ťa potrebuje)	mix
				Wageningen, Netherlands	NGO (Gemeente Wageningen)	mix
6	Preserving Biodiversity	Study Circles	Diverse group of 10-15 adults per Study Circle (ensure diversity in age, gender, occupation and social vulnerability)	Tolmin, Slovenia	NGO (Posoški razvojni center)	rural
				Amaroussion, Greece	Local authority (Municipality of Amaroussion)	urban
				Kilfinane, Ireland	NGO (Ballyhoura Development CLG)	rural
				Stockholm, Sweden	Local authority (Environment and Health Department of the Municipality of Stockholm)	urban

*Note: Rural/urban is based on European Commission (2014), A harmonised definition of Cities and Rural Areas: The new Degree of Urbanisation.

Table A1.2b. Data sources collected from social experiments considered for the secondary analysis

Data source (#DS)	Provided by	Comment / Description
#DS1: WP4 Codebooks of interview data with social experiments participants ¹	SGD consortium members (WP4)	Interviews were conducted by local partners with a variety of participants in social experiments (respecting representative selection criteria), then transcribed and analysed by consortium members. The analysis was guided by specific codes relevant for SSH priority themes - defined ahead - and organized per social experiment stream (Circular Economy, Clean Energy, Efficient Renovation, Sustainable Food, Sustainable Mobility, Preserving Biodiversity), resulting in six codebooks. Per stream, 10 interviews of approx. 30-60 min. were conducted (240 in total).
#DS2: Monthly survey (WP5 questions)	Local partners	At the end of each month, local partners filled in a monthly survey about the ongoing experiments that was prepared by the consortium partners, directed already towards SSH priority themes. (288 surveys in total).
#DS3: Monthly meeting notes (including 12th meeting)	SGD consortium members	Consortium members met with the local partners of each experiment monthly and took note of the developments and progress in the social experiments. For each experiment, the 12th meeting note summarizes all meetings of the past 12 months and reflects on the whole process.
#DS4: Final reflective surveys and experiments' journeys (Responsible Research & innovation (RRI) material)	Local partners	Local partners were given an extensive reflection survey, that included a narrative /qualitative part in which they were asked to reflect and describe the journey of their experiments (24 surveys and 24 experiment journey files (reflections by local partners).
#DS5: RRI interviews with consortium partners	SGD consortium members	The team of WP 6 - Impact evaluation and RRI integration conducted interviews with respective consortium members of each experiment's stream. (6 interviews in total).
#DS6: Applications of Local Partners to host social experiments	Local partners	Shared Green Deal's call for application to host social experiments in the six Green Deal priorities areas received 344 applications in which the candidate organizations (NGO's, association, local authorities (municipalities) detailed how they would conduct the experiments and assure qualitative criteria (i.e. inclusive approach) and commit to previous training provided by the project.
#DS7: Green Deal Topic Webinars	SGD consortium members	Project partners held webinars on each Green Deal priority topic, describing the respective social experiment journeys (https://sharedgreendeal.eu/multimedia/playlist-local-actions-shared-green-deal).

¹ Due to the nature of the qualitative data, openly sharing full datasets would risk compromising participant anonymity. However, anonymised interview transcripts for #DS1 and for each of the six experiment streams are available and can be accessed at the Zenodo platform, community SHARED GREEN DEAL. For **Circular Economy**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Circular Economy [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15387249>; for **Clean Energy**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Clean Energy [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15274546>; for **Efficient Renovations**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Efficient Renovations [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15076033>; for **Sustainable Food**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Sustainable Food [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15387236>; for **Sustainable Mobility**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Sustainable Mobility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15325897>; for **Preserving Biodiversity**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Preserving Biodiversity [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15076035>.

A1.3. Analysis process

A1.3.1. Analysis methodology

We adopted a qualitative, thematic approach to analysis, guided by our four research questions. Our analysis focused on identifying themes relevant to our research questions, rather than testing a specific hypothesis. The method involved an initial inductive phase, in which a thematic framework was developed, followed by two more deductive phases in which the framework was applied and refined, inspired by thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2023). While we did not apply a specific predetermined deductive framework, our later stages of analysis were informed by Bulkeley, Castán Broto and Edwards's (2014) analytical framework for experimental urban climate governance and we ultimately mapped the themes that emerged inductively onto this framework to analyse them in greater depth.

Table A1.3. Overview of linkages between research questions, data sources, and analytical frameworks

Research questions	Data sources to answer the questions	Analytical framework
RQA1. How is the European Green Deal “framed” by local governments and non-governmental organisations within local contexts?	<p>Application data (#DS6) - portions of the application that describe conception of the European Green Deal</p> <p>Field note surveys and meeting notes (#DS2 and #DS3) - mentions of the European Green Deal</p> <p>Final reflections (#DS4) - experiment objectives</p> <p>Webinars (#DS7) - how local European Green Deal challenges/goals are framed</p>	<p>Making experiments: problematisation (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014)</p> <p>Problem framings (Jensen et al., 2019)</p>
RQA2. What European Green Deal objectives are seen as most important to local governance and why?	<p>Application data (#DS6) - portions of the application that describe conception of the European Green Deal goals/objectives</p> <p>Field note surveys and meeting notes (#DS2 and #DS3) - mentions of the European Green Deal goals/objectives</p> <p>Final reflections (#DS4) - experiment objectives</p> <p>Webinars (#DS7) - how local European Green Deal challenges/goals are framed</p>	<p>Making experiments: problematisation (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014)</p> <p>Problem framings (Jensen et al., 2019)</p>
RQA3. What, if any, governance innovations have been brought about by the experiments?	<p>Field note surveys and meeting notes (#DS2 and #DS3) - question on governance</p> <p>Final reflections (#DS4) - portions of which reflect on governance innovations</p> <p>Webinars (#DS7) - what methods local partners used</p>	<p>Making experiments: alignment, rendering technical, rendering compelling (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014)</p> <p>Governance tensions and tactics (Manganelli, 2024a; Manganelli, 2024b)</p>

Research questions	Data sources to answer the questions	Analytical framework
<p>RQA4. How (if at all) have the experiments shifted approaches to public engagement?</p>	<p>Field note surveys and meeting notes (#DS2 and #DS3) - question on governance</p> <p>Final reflections (#DS4) - portions which reflect on changes to public engagement</p> <p>Webinars (#DS7) – planned/expected long-term outcomes of the social experiments</p>	<p>Making experiments: alignment, rendering technical, rendering compelling (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014)</p> <p>Maintaining experiments: upkeep and metabolic adjustment (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014)</p> <p>Living experiments (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014)</p> <p>Embedding experiments in governance processes (Sengers et al., 2021)</p>

A1.3.2. Analysis phases and team roles

The research team consisted of two lead analysis partners, academic researchers at the University of Galway and two secondary analysis partners, practitioners at Energy Cities. The lead analysis partners conducted the analysis and the secondary analysis partners reviewed the analysis, providing comments. To ensure rigor, three online meetings were held during the preparation of the analysis plan and analysis to discuss ideas and challenges. In addition, teams conducting the other SHARED GREEN DEAL thematic analyses provided feedback prior to and during the analysis.

The research team used NVivo qualitative analysis software to analyse the data. The coding process had three phases:

1. Initial inductive phase to develop a basic code structure. This phase involved a single analyst coding all data sources through “top-level” coding, which generated a relatively small number of broad code categories, rather than a large number of detailed codes. This was presented to the research team in the form of an initial codebook and feedback gathered.
2. Drafting a refined codebook. Based on the feedback, the analyst reviewed the coding to generate a refined codebook. The codebook was shared with the team and feedback incorporated into phase 3.
3. Deductive phase to apply the coding framework. This phase involved reviewing the coding of all data sources and developing more fine-grained codes within the broad categories already established. The results were shared with the team and final feedback incorporated.

A1.3.3. Limitations

First, our analysis focused on the perspective of the local partners running the social experiments rather than the perspectives of all participants. We believe that the data sources representing local partners nevertheless present valuable perspectives on experimental governance in SHARED GREEN DEAL, as these actors were most knowledgeable about the process. Second, data collection ended within six months of finalising the experiments and there were few opportunities to follow up with the local partners after this. Although we cannot predict how the experiments will develop in the long term, the data collected in the immediate aftermath of the experiment still provides an indication of what factors are in place for their expected continuation.

A1.4. Coding framework

The following coding framework was developed through the analysis in NVivo.

Table A1.4. SHARED GREEN DEAL governance analysis coding framework

Name	Description
1. MAKING experiments	This category covers codes related to the first stage of experimental urban governance: “conceiving, framing, and operationalizing the will to improve in relation to climate change” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 42). It consists of both understanding how climate change can be understood as a challenge through “problematization,” delimiting the field of intervention for acting upon the challenge, and practices to improve. In SHARED GREEN DEAL, this consists of most stages of the social experiments.
1.1 Problematization	This sub-category covers how social experiment actors understand “questions of risk and security in environmental, economic... political [and other] terms” and the “opportunities and the potential to create alternative futures” through social experiments (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 44).
1.1.a.1. European Green Deal	This code covers specific references to the European Green Deal or EU policy in relation to the experiment or the organisation’s work throughout the course of the experiment.
1.1.a.2. Application - European Green Deal, EU policy	This code covers specific references to the European Green Deal or EU policy in relation to the experiment or the organisation’s work in the SHARED GREEN DEAL project application.
1.1.b. Problem framings	This code covers problem framings, or specifically defining how the organisation understands the challenge that must be addressed and the purpose of the social experiment. This draws on the following definition of “problem framings”: “the process of defining the purpose and outcomes of innovative activity as well as delineation of the ‘thing’ that undergoes change” (Jensen et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2010).
1.1.b.1. Disconnected actors	This problem framing identifies that in order to solve certain sustainability challenges, actors that hold different types of expertise or serve different functions in a community must be connected.
1.1.b.2. Economically unsustainable environmentally friendly options	This problem framing refers to the fact that in some sectors and locations, environmentally friendly options are not considered economically viable.
Specific focus on those in economically or socially vulnerable conditions	
1.1.b.3. Environmental and health conditions	Existing poor environmental or health conditions, those that are actively deteriorating, or those that are predicted in a given location.
1.1.b.4. Lack of education and awareness	This problem framing refers to the absence of awareness, knowledge, or information among key groups about certain sustainability challenges or solutions.
1.1.b.5. Lack of inclusion and participation	This problem framing refers to the absence of key groups in decision-making, policy, planning, or action on sustainability challenges.
1.1.b.6. Policy gaps	This problem framing identifies where national/regional/local policy does not specifically or sufficiently address a sustainability challenge.

Name	Description
1.1.b.7. Unsustainable social practices or individual behaviours	This problem framing identifies the central thing that needs to be changed as shared practices or individual behaviours that are considered harmful to the environment, nature, safety, or health.
1.1.c.1. Goals - experiment	This code focuses on the expected outcomes of the social experiment, in reference to the following definition of “problem framings”: “the process of defining the purpose and outcomes of innovative activity as well as delineation of the ‘thing’ that undergoes change” (Jensen et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2010).
1.2 Aligning multiple actors	This sub-category covers “practices of assembling a programme of improvement through which [problems] can be addressed”; “bringing into productive relation the different parties and... material elements that constitute the field of intervention” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 44).
1.2.a. Developing supportive environment for experiment	This set of codes covers practices and dynamics related to the organisers’ attempts to draw on or create an environment that would support the experiment and help it succeed.
1.2.a.1. Application - embeddedness of experiment	This code covers how the experiment proposed will be embedded in the existing governance of the problem from the perspective of the local partner.
1.2.b.1.a. Application - synergies with existing projects	This code covers the ways in which the experiment proposed will have synergies with existing projects the local partner is engaged in.
1.2.a.2. Application - international, national, regional, local policy	This code covers mentions of formal governance documents at the international, national, regional, or local level in relation to the experiments and the organisation’s work. It also covers mentions of belonging to international governance networks. It may also include an assessment of the policies (i.e. shortcomings, effectiveness, etc.).
1.2.a.3. Community partners, intermediaries, & facilitators - organising work with	This code covers descriptions of how the organisers collaborated with different community partners, intermediaries, and facilitators to plan and execute the social experiment.
1.2.a.4. Connection with other initiatives	This code covers how the social experiment was connected to or aligned with other initiatives, either in the past or ongoing.
1.2.a.5. Government interactions	This code covers the ways in which social experiment organisers involved formal government from various scales in their experiment, including whether government served to aid the experiment, hinder it, or had an ambiguous impact.
1.2.b.5.a. Application - policymakers & government engagement, expected	This code covers how organisations expect to involve policymakers and government actors in the experiment, or how they are already connected with policymakers and government. It does not include how the experiment will contribute to policymaking and governance, unless there is an overlap/ ambiguity in how they refer to these actors’ engagement in the experiment and in its follow-up.
1.2.a.6. SHARED GREEN DEAL support for local partners	This code covers the ways in which the SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium provided various kinds of help for the social experiment organisers throughout the course of planning and executing the experiments.
1.2.b. Participant ownership	This set of codes covers to what degree the participants were engaged in the social experiment.
1.2.b.1. Initiative, responsibility, ownership - participants taking	This code covers instances in which the participants took initiative, responsibility, or ownership for various aspects of running the experiment, its activities, and its outcomes.

Name	Description
1.2.b.2. Roles of participants	This code covers the types of roles participants took on during the course of the social experiments; what they contributed.
1.2.b.3. Getting feedback from participants	This code covers instances where social experiment organisers requested feedback on the process from participants, as well as how the feedback was used (where applicable).
1.2.c. Participant alignment	This set of codes explicitly covers the ways in which different participants were brought together to undertake the social experiment.
1.2.c.1. Aligning participants' goals and activities	This code covers descriptions of how the social experiments led to the alignment of participants' different interests, goals, knowledge, and actions in a coordinated effort to address the given climate change / sustainability challenge.
1.2.c.2. Diversity impacts	This code covers the ways in which diversity helped foster collaboration or served as an impediment to collaboration.
1.2.c.3. Shared values of participants	This code covers instances in which social experiment participants shared values and how this impacted their collaboration.
1.2.c.4. Value of different expertise forms	This code covers expressions of appreciation for different types of knowledge being present in the experiment and how this contributed to the experiments' goals.
1.2.c.5. Challenging cultural beliefs	This code covers the ways in which the experiment presented a challenge to existing cultural beliefs in the experiment location, particularly among those engaged in the experiment.
1.3 Rendering technical	This sub-category covers the way social experiment actors "seek... to test and experience what it means to respond to climate change, and of establishing what improvement entails..." (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 44). "[T]he unfolding in time and space of uncertain elements, in which the work involved in addressing climate change is contingent and bounded to a particular urban locale, yet open to multiple possibilities" (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 45).

Name	Description
1.3.a. Experiment activities	<p>This set of codes covers the social experiment itself: the specific activities that constituted the experiment. <i>Note: We do not define each of these as the code name clearly describes the experiment activity.</i></p>
1.3.a.1. Capacity building workshops	
1.3.a.10. Learning experiences	
1.3.a.11. Preparing recommendations	
1.3.a.12. Final event - celebration	
1.3.a.12. Final event - conference	
1.3.a.12. Final event - exhibition	
1.3.a.2. Collecting good practices	
1.3.a.3. Collecting information from participants & public	
1.3.a.4. Creating an online networking platform	
1.3.a.5. Creative arts	
1.3.a.6. Design thinking prototyping and feedback	
1.3.a.7. Discussions and planning with participants	
1.3.a.8. Game	
1.3.a.9. Interactive workshops	
1.3.b. Modifications to experiment activities	<p>This set of codes covers how the experiment activities were altered for various reasons over the course of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project.</p>
1.3.b.1. Modifying plans to fit experiment, participant needs	<p>This code covers specific instances in which organisers decided to change their plans in order to meet the needs that arose, either from participants, organisers, or other contextual factors.</p>
1.3.b.2. Changing approaches	<p>This code refers to organisers' decisions to change their approach to the experiment or a specific aspect of it during the project.</p>
1.3.b.3. Flexibility, adaptation	<p>This code covers instances in which organisers took a flexible approach to a specific aspect of their social experiment rather than sticking to a rigid plan.</p>
1.3.b.4. Feasibility, project constraints	<p>This code covers whether organisers were able to implement certain aspects of their social experiments in the context of the project, and questions/reflections on this.</p>
1.3.b.5. Guidelines - using those provided by SHARED GREEN DEAL	<p>This code covers the ways in which the organisers' adapted the guidelines provided by the SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium for each experiment to their local context and reflections on how this process worked.</p>
1.3.c. Method - reflections	<p>This code covers organisers' reflections on the methods that they used, including what they learned from those methods.</p>

Name	Description
1.4 Rendering compelling	This sub-category covers the ways in which social experiment organisers “test out” how to “persuade, cajole and induce others to participate in that which is uncertain and where the rewards are unclear” and the broader “emotional and affective work” required to undertake an experiment (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 45).
1.4.a. Sustaining engagement	This set of codes covers the ways in which social experiment organisers sought to keep participants involved, participant feelings towards the experiments, and challenges in ensuring participants’ continued engagement.
1.4.a.1. Appreciation for experiment	This code covers participants’ and organisers’ expressions of gratitude for the social experiment.
1.4.a.1.a. Enjoying activities	This code covers reports of participants enjoying social experiment activities.
1.4.a.1.b. Enthusiasm, high interest	This code covers participants’ expressions of enthusiasm for the social experiment activities and outcomes.
1.4.a.2. Attendance	This code covers participant attendance at social experiment events, including sufficient and low attendance.
1.4.a.2.a. Scheduling difficulties	This code covers the difficulties organisers faced when scheduling social experiment activities.
1.4.a.2.b. Turnover, dropouts, replacements, new members	This code covers instances of turnover, dropouts, replacements, and new members, particularly relevant for experiments which requested participation in a series of events.
1.4.a.3. Welcoming atmosphere	This code covers the ways in which organisers succeeded in making their events feel welcoming and supportive of active participation.
1.4.a.4. Compensation	This code covers ways in which participants were “compensated” for their time spent participating in the social experiment.
1.4.a.5. Sharing a meal	This code covers descriptions of participants eating together.
1.4.a.6. Practical and logistical considerations	This code covers practical and logistical considerations (various, not covered under other codes) that social experiment organisers needed to consider when planning and running experiment events.
1.4.a.6.a. Making it manageable for participants	This code covers the ways in which organisers tried to make the activities easier for participants to take part in.
1.4.a.7. Participation styles - different	This code covers the different participation styles encountered in experiment activities.
1.4.a.7.a. Lack of engagement	This code covers instances of low or absent participant engagement in the experiment.
1.4.a.7.b. Opening up over course of experiment	This code covers descriptions of how participants became more willing to participate as the experiment or an experiment activity went on.
1.4.a.8. Challenges to experiment, other	This code covers challenges to the experiment not covered in other codes.
1.4.b. Relationships	This set of codes covers the ways in which social experiment organisers and participants formed relationships during the course of the project and in what ways these facilitated the experiment and/or its follow-up.
1.4.b.1. Beneficial connections	This code covers connections that organisers and participants made through the experiment process that were beneficial for them longer-term.

Name	Description
1.4.b.2. Building relationships	This code covers descriptions of how organisers and participants built relationships through the process of engaging in the experiments.
1.4.b.3. Building trust	This code covers descriptions of how organisers and participants built trust through the process of engaging in the experiments.
1.4.b.4. Difficult relationships	This code describes relationships between participants that included tensions or conflicts.
2. MAINTAINING & LIVING experiments	This category combines stages 2 and 3 of the experimental urban climate governance framework (since these are less observable in the data collected as part of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments). This category refers to practices that describe how experiments, once made, are extended beyond their initial experiment period and become (or fail to become) part of everyday life. For SHARED GREEN DEAL, this category is related to what happened as a result of the experiments and what happened after they finished.
2.1 Maintaining - Upkeep and metabolic adjustment	This sub-category refers to how social experiments become practices that “are engaged in the workings of different forms of circulation and the extent that they involve ‘organizing, or anyway allowing the development of ever-wider circuits’ (Foucault 2009: 45)” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 45).
2.1.a. Results and follow-up	This set of codes covers the social experiments’ immediate outcomes and ways in which these will be or are already being pursued by organisers or participants.
2.1.a.1. Desire to continue work after SHARED GREEN DEAL	This code covers expressions of organisers’ and participants’ interest in continuing the work started in SHARED GREEN DEAL following the end of the experiment, either by continuing the experiment or modifying it.
2.1.a.2. Follow-up projects and actions	This code covers specific projects that organisers and participants are undertaking following the social experiment or specific actions they have taken as a result of the experiment.
2.1.a.3. Improved networking, collaboration, communication	This code covers how the experiment contributed to improved networking, collaboration, and/or communication between organisers, participants, and other actors.
2.1.a.4. Proposals, recommendations, visions, narratives	This code covers proposals, recommendations, visions, and narratives that resulted from the social experiment.
2.1.a.5. Sharing learnings	This code covers instances in which a key outcome of the experiments was the sharing of knowledge learned among peers or other institutions/organisations.
2.1.a.6. Following up with participants	This code covers how social experiment organisers sought to follow up with participants following the experiment.
2.1.a.7. Feelings of confidence, having been listened to	This code covers how the experiment resulted in participants feeling more confident or that they had been listened to.
2.1.a.8. Funding, resources for follow-up programmes	This code covers statements about the necessity for and availability of funding for continuing the work done as part of SHARED GREEN DEAL.
2.1.a.9. Upkeep of experiment	This code covers ways in which the social experiment organisers sought to continue the experiment and in which ways they needed to modify it in order for it to be fit for purpose.
2.1.b. Learning	This set of codes includes all statements regarding how the social experiments led to different kinds of learning.
2.1.b.1. Learning - content	This code covers what participants learned about the topic of their social experiments.

Name	Description
2.1.b.2. Learning - new skills	This code covers new skills (concrete and soft) that participants learned during their social experiments.
2.1.b.3. Learning - local partner	This code covers what the social experiment organisers / local partners learned from the experiment.
2.1.b.4. Increased appreciation of local or experiential knowledge	This code covers statements about how the experiment contributed to increased appreciation for non-expert knowledge, such as that arising from local communities or practical experience.
2.1.c. Policy connection	This code covers how the outputs, outcomes, and results of the experiment were formulated in relation to policy and communicated with an intent to impact policy.
2.1.d. Duration of experiment	This code covers reflections on the one-year duration of the experiment.
2.1.e. Unexpected developments & outcomes	This code covers surprising developments, unintended consequences, and unexpected outcomes that the experiments had.
2.1.f. Experimental understandings of	This code covers reflections on how the social experiments were “experimental” and what the word “experimental” meant in practice to organisers and the SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium.
2.2 Living - conduct, subjectivity, contestation, neglect	This sub-category covers the ways in which social experiments become “taken up in the day-to-day practices of the individuals and institutions that are subject to forms of governmental intervention” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 47). Experimentation becomes a “lived practice” but also exposes its own limits. It involves the “creation of climate subjectivities, as well as the ways in which they are resisted, circumvented and ignored” (Bulkeley, Castán Broto, and Edwards, 2014, p. 42).
2.2.a. Long-term outcomes, expected	This code covers descriptions of longer-term outcomes resulting from the social experiments.
2.2.b. Engagement innovations	This set of codes covers how the experiment led to innovations in engagement, participation, and communication mechanisms at the local level.
2.2.b.1. New, different ways of working	This code covers how the experiments represented new, different ways of working that became or were expected to become established in ways of working following the end of the social experiments.

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Appendix A2. Policy context and Governance Pathways

Table A2.1. SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment streams⁷

Experiment stream	Policy context	Related European Green Deal policies	Experimental method	Experiment sites
Clean Energy	“Energy accounted for over 75% of EU greenhouse gases in 2021. Decarbonising the EU’s energy system is critical to achieve 2030 climate objectives and climate neutrality by 2050. However, a successful transition to renewables must meaningfully include all levels of society to be just.”	Solar Energy Strategy, Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy, Renewable Energy Directive	Community visioning <i>A process which brings a diverse group of people together to imagine a desired future, with the theme of ‘clean energy’</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fonden Motorfabrikken Marstal and Blue Innovators, Ærø, Denmark Diptuación de Granada, Granada, Spain Alliance of Associations Polish Green Network, Bełchatów, Poland Essex County Council, Essex, UK
Circular Economy	“The EU’s transition to a circular economy aims to reduce the strain on natural resources, promote sustainable growth, and create new jobs, all while supporting the 2050 climate neutrality targets and biodiversity conservation.”	Circular Economy Action Plan	Local accelerator hubs <i>A physical and online interactive space offering support to connect local stakeholders, enabling businesses to experiment, pilot, and scale innovations</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cyprus Organization for Standardization (CYS), Nicosia/Limassol/Larnaca, Cyprus Camara Municipal de Santo Tirso, Santo Tirso, Portugal Technology Park Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia Val de Marne en Transition, Val-de-Marne, France

⁷ From Kovács et al., 2024

Experiment stream	Policy context	Related European Green Deal policies	Experimental method	Experiment sites
Efficient Renovations	“Buildings account for about 40% of Europe’s total energy use, highlighting the urgent need for greater energy efficiency renovations. Indeed, the European Union has set ambitious targets for renovating Europe’s old and energy inefficient building stock via its Renovation Wave Strategy.”	Renovation Wave Strategy	Knowledge networks <i>Multi-stakeholder groups who share a common interest in learning through doing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Habitat for Humanity Magyarország Alapítvány, Nógrád County, Hungary Mayo County Council, Louisburgh locality including Clare Island and Inishturk Island, Ireland Let’s renovate the city, Vilnius, Lithuania ECODES, Zaragoza, Spain
Sustainable Mobility	“The European Green Deal includes a target to reduce transport-related greenhouse gas emissions by 90% by 2050. In this context, the European Commission points out that also public and private organisations, such as schools, should be encouraged to develop mobility actions that promote low- and zero-emission transportation means.”	European Urban Mobility Framework	School mobility labs <i>A ‘real life’ testing environment where citizens are involved in the design, testing, co-creation and adoption of new solutions</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental center for Administration and Technology (ECAT), Kaunas, Lithuania Sofia Development Association (SDA), project SOfiaGREEN, Sofia, Bulgaria Municipality of Braga, Braga, Portugal An Mheitheal Rothar, Galway, Ireland
Sustainable Food	“[T]he European Commission has published its Farm to Fork Strategy, which sets out ambitious targets and aims for Europe... developing more sustainable food systems.”	Farm to Fork Strategy	Transition assemblies <i>A collective process of understanding, learning, visioning, and experimenting around specific societal transition challenges</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REFORMATEN, Stockholm, Sweden ASFODELO, Cella Monte, Italy Gemeente Wageningen, Wageningen, Netherlands Klíma ťa potrebuje, City of Košice, Slovakia
Preserving Biodiversity	“Loss of biodiversity and habitats, and the services they provide, is an existential threat to Europe. Societal transformations are needed to deliver on the EU Green Deal ambition of making 30% of Europe protected areas, and restoring at least 20% of its land and at sea by 2030 (and all degraded ecosystems by 2050).”	EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030	Study circles <i>Non-formal, experiential, collaborative, and self-directed approaches to learning in participative discussion groups</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Posoški razvojni center, Tolmin, Slovenia Ballyhoura Development CLG, Kilfinane, Ireland Environment and health department, City of Stockholm, Stockholm, Sweden Municipality of Amaroussion, Athens, Greece

Table A2.2. SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments: experimental governance pathways⁸

Priority area (thematic stream)	Experiment name	Location	Context (rural/urban) ⁸	Local partner organisation	Local partner type	Problem framing types	Experimental activities	Governance innovations
Clean Energy	Energy Futures of Aero's Island Community ⁹	Ærø, Denmark	Rural	Fonden Motorfabrikken Marstal and Blue Innovators	NGO	Lack of inclusion and participation, Economic unsustainability of environmentally friendly options	n/a	n/a
	Granada: Community Visions for Community Energy	Granada, Spain	Mix	Diptuación de Granada	Local authority	Lack of inclusion and participation	Workshops – capacity building, planning/ discussing	Educational innovation Relational innovation Organisational innovation
	The future starts now: design the tomorrow of Bełchatów	Bełchatów, Poland	Mix	Alliance of Associations Polish Green Network	NGO	Lack of inclusion and participation, Economic unsustainability of environmentally friendly options	Workshops – creative arts, discussions and planning, interactive	Education innovation Relational innovation Policy inclusion innovation
	Jaywick's stories of change: improving energy and health futures	Jaywick, UK	Rural	Essex County Council	Local authority	Lack of inclusion and participation, Focus on environmentally and socially vulnerable	Workshops – interactive	Relational innovation Organisational innovation Policy inclusion innovation

⁸ Rural/urban designations are based on [European Commission \(2014\), A harmonised definition of Cities and Rural Areas: The new Degree of Urbanisation](#).

⁹ The social experiment in Ærø, Denmark was begun but not finished. The experiment ended early in January 2024 due to a change in partner circumstances, which meant that community visioning workshops and interviews did not take place. Due to this, we were not able to assess the experiment activities and governance innovations for the purposes of this report.

Priority area (thematic stream)	Experiment name	Location	Context (rural/urban)	Local partner organisation	Local partner type	Problem framing types	Experimental activities	Governance innovations
Circular Economy	Importance of standardisation towards the circular economy in Cyprus	Nicosia/ Limassol/ Larnaca, Cyprus	Mix	Cyprus Organization for Standardization (CYS)	National authority	Lack of education and awareness, Disconnected actors, Unsustainable social practices / individual behaviour	Workshops – interactive, Collecting good practices, Creating an online platform, Collecting information from participants/public	Education innovation Relational innovation Organisational innovation
	Investment as a key enabler for the circular economy in Santo Tirso	Santo Tirso, Portugal	Urban	Camara Municipal de Santo Tirso	Local authority	Disconnected actors	Workshops – interactive, Collecting good practices, Creating an online platform	Education innovation Relational innovation Organisational innovation
	Industry 4.0 and circular economy in Ljubljana	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Urban	Technology Park Ljubljana	Local authority	Unsustainable social practices / individual behaviour	Workshops – interactive, Collecting good practices, Creating an online platform	Education innovation Organisational innovation
	Innovative sufficiency solutions and business models for circular economy in the textile sector in Val-de-Marne	Val-de-Marne, France	Urban	Val de Marne en Transition	NGO	Economic unsustainability of environmentally friendly options, Unsustainable social practices / individual behaviour	Workshops – discussions and planning; Collecting good practices; Creating an online platform; Collecting information from participants/public	Education innovation Relational innovation Organisational innovation

Priority area (thematic stream)	Experiment name	Location	Context (rural/urban)	Local partner organisation	Local partner type	Problem framing types	Experimental activities	Governance innovations
Efficient renovations	Green Homes in Nógrád	Nógrád County, Hungary	Rural	Habitat for Humanity Magyarország Alapítvány	NGO	Economic unsustainability of economically friendly options, Focus on economically/ socially vulnerable	Workshops – discussions and planning; Learning experiences; Collecting information from participants/ public	Education innovation Relational innovation Policy inclusion innovation
	Communicating the benefits and sharing renovation know-how in Louisburgh	Louisburgh locality including Clare Island and Inishturk Island, Ireland	Rural	Mayo County Council	Regional authority / NGO	Lack of education and awareness, Economic unsustainability of environmentally friendly options, Focus on economically/ socially vulnerable	Workshops – discussions and planning; Learning experiences; Collecting information from participants/ public	Education innovation Relational innovation Policy inclusion innovation
	Broadening the role of One-Stop-Shops in Efficient building renovation in Vilnius	Vilnius, Lithuania	Urban	Let's renovate the city	Local authority	Lack of education and awareness, Disconnected actors, Unsustainable social practices / individual behaviour	Workshops – capacity building, discussions and planning; Learning experiences; Collecting information from participants/ public	Education innovation Relational innovation
	Sharing knowledge for efficient renovation of residential buildings in Zaragoza	Zaragoza, Spain	Urban	ECODES	NGO	Economic unsustainability of environmentally friendly options, Focus on economically/ socially vulnerable	Workshops – capacity building, discussions and planning, interactive; Learning experiences; Games; Preparing recommendations	Education innovation Relational innovation

Priority area (thematic stream)	Experiment name	Location	Context (rural/urban)	Local partner organisation	Local partner type	Problem framing types	Experimental activities	Governance innovations
Sustainable Mobility	Panevėžys Sustainable School Mobility Lab	Panevėžys, Lithuania	Urban	Environmental center for Administration and Technology (ECAT)	NGO	Lack of inclusion and participation, Lack of education and awareness, Unsustainable social practices / individual behaviour, Policy gaps	Workshops – creative arts, discussions and planning, interactive; Learning experiences; Games; Preparing and presenting recommendations	Education innovation Policy inclusion innovation
	Sofia Sustainable School Mobility Lab	Sofia, Bulgaria	Urban	Sofia Development Association (SDA), project SOfiaGREEN	NGO	Unsustainable social practices / individual behaviour	Workshops – creative arts, discussions and planning, interactive; Learning experiences; Collecting information from participants/public; Preparing and presenting recommendations	Education innovation Policy inclusion innovation
	Braga Sustainable School Mobility Lab	Braga, Portugal	Urban	Municipality of Braga	Local authority	Unsustainable social practices / individual behaviour	Workshops – creative arts, discussions and planning, interactive; Learning experiences; Preparing, presenting, and implementing recommendations	Education innovation Policy inclusion innovation
	Galway Sustainable School Mobility Lab	Galway, Ireland	Urban	An Mheitheal Rothar	NGO	Unsustainable social practices / individual behaviour	Workshops – creative arts, discussions and planning, interactive; Learning experiences; Collecting information from participants/public; Preparing and presenting recommendations	Education innovation Policy inclusion innovation

Priority area (thematic stream)	Experiment name	Location	Context (rural/urban)	Local partner organisation	Local partner type	Problem framing types	Experimental activities	Governance innovations
Sustainable Food	Stockholm food environment	Stockholm, Sweden	Urban	REFORMATEN	NGO	Lack of education and awareness, Policy gaps	Workshops – interactive, creative arts; Preparing recommendations	Relational innovation Policy inclusion innovation
	Local Change towards More Sustainable food production	Cella Monte, Italy	Rural	ASFODELO	NGO	Lack of education and awareness, Disconnected actors	Workshops – interactive; Preparing recommendations	Relational innovation Policy inclusion innovation
	Strengthening food governance and biocultural restoration in the Zuid Veluwe bioregion	Wageningen, Netherlands	Mix	Gemeente Wageningen	NGO	Lack of inclusion and participation, Economic unsustainability of environmentally friendly options, Disconnected actors	Workshops – creative arts, discussions and planning, interactive; Learning experiences	Education innovation Relational innovation
	Sustainable Food Systems in Košice	City of Košice, Slovakia	Mix	Klíma ěa potrebuje	NGO	Disconnected actors, Policy gaps	Workshops – discussions and planning, interactive; Learning experiences	Education innovation Relational innovation

Priority area (thematic stream)	Experiment name	Location	Context (rural/urban)	Local partner organisation	Local partner type	Problem framing types	Experimental activities	Governance innovations
Preserving biodiversity	Hot spot – nature writes stories and people with it	Tolmin, Slovenia	Rural	Posoški razvojni center	NGO	Lack of education and awareness	Workshops – creative arts, discussions and planning; Learning experiences	Education innovation Relational innovation
	Stop, Look and Listen: Preserving the Biodiversity of Ballyhoura	Kilfinane, Ireland	Rural	Ballyhoura Development CLG	NGO	Lack of education and awareness	Workshops – creative arts; Learning experiences	Education innovation Relational innovation
	Stockholm Biodiversity Learning Experiment – by participating and doing (SBLE)	Stockholm, Sweden	Urban	Environment and health department, City of Stockholm	Local authority	Lack of education and awareness, Focus on economically/ socially vulnerable	Workshops – creative arts, discussions and planning; Learning experiences	Education innovation Relational innovation
	Amaroussion Biodiversity Local Experiment (ABLE)	Athens, Greece	Urban	Municipality of Amaroussion	Local authority	Lack of education and awareness	Workshops – creative arts; Learning experiences	Education innovation Relational innovation

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